

Donor- π -Acceptor Conjugated Organic Dyes for Efficient Dye-Sensitized Solar Cells.

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Harvesting solar energy is one of the hot areas of current research as they offer greener and sustainable way of meeting the energy needs of the modern society. In this context, photovoltaic cells, devices which convert solar energy directly into electrical energy, are of prime importance. Among the various dye sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) have emerged as one of the leading third generation photovoltaic technologies.¹The main advantageous of DSSCs are simplicity of design, architecture, and cost effectiveness, and can be easily fabricated with minimum investment. It consists of a photosensitizer (dye) adsorbed onto semiconductor (TiO₂ or ZnO) which act as a photoanode, an electrolyte and a counter electrode.²The dye absorbs solar light and transfers an electron to the conduction band of a metal oxide semiconductor. The dye gets regenerated by accepting an electron from the electrolyte which is then revived by the catalytic redox reaction at the counter electrode. The efficiency of DSSCs is mainly determined by the character of the dye employed. Ease of synthesis, ability to tune its opto-electronic properties by structural control, high stability and less toxicity makes completely organic based dyes as promising candidates for this technology. Herein we demonstrate design and synthesis of thiophene based donor- π -acceptor conjugated organic dyes for DSSC applications. The solar cells fabricated out of these simple dyes yielded efficiencies above 8 %.

Solar energy conversion, dye-sensitized solar cells, donor- π -acceptor conjugated organic dyes, renewable energy

References

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